

Strategies for rapid learning in SuperPro Designer through a course on biotechnological process planning

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Abstract

Incorporating digital tools into engineering education is crucial for preparing students to solve real-world challenges. This study explores the use of SuperPro Designer as an active learning tool in a biotechnological process planning course, integrating Problem-Based Learning (PBL) and Project-Based Learning (PjBL) methodologies. The course aimed to accelerate software proficiency while improving interdisciplinary understanding of bioreactor scale-up, economic assessment, sustainability, and industrial regulations. Students were first introduced to SuperPro Designer through guided practical exercises available via live sessions and recordings. They then engaged in a PBL-based challenge, where they scaled up a bioreactor and assessed its economic and environmental impact. Finally, students conducted an open-ended bioprocess design project, selecting a product, defining a market strategy, and performing a techno-economic feasibility analysis. This structure encouraged critical thinking and real-world problem-solving. Student performance was assessed through a pre-test and post-test comparison using Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test, revealing a significant shift toward high proficiency levels. A post-course survey further highlighted that student, regardless of proficiency level, reported high confidence in key bioprocess design skills, reinforcing the effectiveness of this approach. These findings suggest that integrating digital tools with active learning strategies can effectively bridge theoretical knowledge and practical application in engineering education. This approach is transferable to other engineering disciplines that require techno-economic analysis, strategic planning and scale-up decision-making.

Keywords: SuperPro, Bioprocess, Scale-up, Project-Based Learning, Engineering Education, Simulation-Based Learning, Bioprocess Simulation, Techno-Economic Analysis

1 Introduction

Nowadays, bioprocess engineering courses integrate various innovative teaching strategies to enhance student comprehension, and the application of concepts related to the modern biotechnological industry. These courses emphasize teaching industrial-scale fermentation design and control, solving open-ended design problems, and acquiring practical fermentation skills. Undergraduate students gain a comprehensive understanding of biochemical processes, industrial biotechnology fundamentals, kinetics, and reactor calculations (Alam & Zakaria, 2021; Anakin & McDowell, 2021; Pazos et al., 2011). Courses typically cover unit operations such as sterilization, aeration, and stirring in bioreactors, progressing to the scale-up of biochemical processes. To achieve these objectives, diverse teaching strategies are employed, including lectures, tutorials, practical work, discussions, collaborative learning, small group discussions, journal reflections, case-based learning, lab work, service-learning projects, and industrial visits (Pazos et al., 2010). The continuous development of new learning materials aims to advance bioprocess engineering education, leading to high student satisfaction and active participation. Furthermore, the use of computational tools to support cooperative learning methods has shown significant improvement in student cognitive skills (Ballesteros Martin & Moral Rama, 2014; Martín-Lara & Ronda, 2020). Meticulously designed engineering courses that integrate theoretical and practical aspects, along with competencies like communication and teamwork, ensure comprehensive student learning. In this context of continuous improvement, the use of process simulators can significantly enhance student learning and engagement. Particularly, the use of SuperPro Designer, which contains a unique environment of process units fitting common bioprocess equipment, provides a

technological platform for students to model not only bioreactor operations under various conditions but several process units related to recovery and purification of bioproducts (downstream processing). This promotes a hands-on approach to learning that extends beyond theoretical concepts (Alam & Zakaria, 2021) or scholar lab experiments. The use of SuperPro Designer in education can significantly enhance students' competencies in biotechnological process planning and evaluation. The robustness of the software has been proven by several scientific articles devoted to systematically assessing the technical and economic viability of various processes, such as natural pigments production (Mora-Jiménez et al., 2024), alginate and fucoidan production from sargassum (Ramírez-Partida et al., 2024), recombinant protein production (Alkanaimsh et al., 2024), lipids production from microalgae (Valdovinos-García et al., 2024), bioethanol production from starch milk (Katanski et al., 2024), to name a few of the most recently published studies. Integrating the use of SuperPro into common bioprocess engineering courses at early stages of the academic life of Biochemical or Biotechnology engineering students is of great importance. The software supports the creation and analysis of complex mathematical models, essential for predicting and optimizing bioreactor performance, and provides students with advanced digital skills. To articulate biotechnological development, SuperPro Designer enables students to generate detailed quantitative and qualitative data for scientific arguments. It facilitates process documentation and report generation, supporting well-founded arguments in scientific texts and presentations. The software also allows students to simulate scenarios and assess the economic, social, and environmental impacts of their designs. This capability aids in constructing robust, scientifically validated arguments and fosters critical communication skills, essential for engaging diverse audiences in scientific and professional forums.

In this context, the main objective of this article is to design and apply strategies for accelerating mastery in SuperPro Designer by utilizing a course focused on biotechnological process planning. SuperPro Designer, therefore, plays a pivotal role in demonstrating key competencies in the articulation of biotechnological development as well as in biotechnological process planning and evaluation.

2 Methods and experimental settings

The course selected for this study was titled 'Planning of Biotechnological Processes'. It is an intensive 5-week course (16 hours a week) imparted to students in the 6th semester of Biotechnological Engineering at Tecnológico de Monterrey. The core of this course is the design, modeling, optimization, and technical and economic evaluation of a given bioprocess to produce a biomolecule of industrial interest. The total number of students impacted in this study was 40, divided into 2 groups due to the availability of the computing classroom where the SuperPro Designer v12.0 was installed. The students had no previous experience in the use of SuperPro Designer or biotechnological process planning. However, they did have experience using modeling software like Mathematica and Matlab. Additionally, the students took two previous courses focused on the usage of bioreactors for carrying out different experimental cultures and a course on bioseparation strategies tailored to biomolecule physicochemical characteristics.

2.1 Teaching strategies

Methods and teaching techniques employed in the course include a combination of theoretical analysis, practical applications, case studies, practical exercises (one activity), and assessments (two exams). Presentations of situational problems and evidence-based evaluations are also included. Support tools comprise tutorials, instructional videos, discussion forums, and extensive tutoring sessions. Our teaching strategy is principally rooted in Project-Based Learning (PjBL), a learner-centered approach that promotes deep learning through the development of real-world projects, emphasizing teamwork, knowledge integration, and artifact creation (Guo et al., 2020). In engineering education, PjBL not only facilitates content mastery but also

fosters transversal competences such as design thinking, collaboration, and effective communication (Bes-Piá et al., 2023). These aspects were embedded in the course through simulation-based design challenges using SuperPro Designer, supported by guided resources and iterative feedback. We further encourage collaborative learning to address complex problems, fostering teamwork and communication skills. Continuous assessment methods monitor student progress and guide learning effectively. Digital resources enrich the experience, with tutorials, instructional videos (which can be consulted per request to the corresponding author), and online forums, allowing students to learn at their own pace and revisit complex topics as needed. Based on performance, students' proficiency in SuperPro Designer was classified as follows: proficient (91–100 points), solid (81–90), basic (71–80), and incipient (below 70).

2.2 SuperPro designer educational strategies

SuperPro Designer is a comprehensive software tool that primarily performs two essential processes: material and energy balances for each piece of equipment specified in the process diagram, and economic analysis of all aspects defined within the process diagram. To operate effectively, the software requires various types of information of a biotechnological process. Experimental data is crucial, including cell culture data, operational data of bioreactors, and separation and purification data. Theoretical information is also necessary, such as the physical and chemical properties of components, material and energy balances, equipment design parameters, and mathematical models and design equations. Additionally, SuperPro Designer incorporates supplementary information like raw material costs, auxiliary services, equipment expenses, regulations and standards, and market data. By integrating this comprehensive data set, SuperPro Designer facilitates detailed and accurate modelling, analysis, and optimization of bioprocesses, allowing for informed decision-making and efficient design and operational planning. It was proposed to follow a smart sequence of steps for the fast learning of this important tool, which comprises the following steps: (i) Start by defining the process diagram to establish a clear visual representation of the workflow. (ii) Next, enter all relevant data, including experimental, theoretical, and supplementary information. (iii) Proceed with the simulation and optimization phase, where the process is modelled, and its efficiency is enhanced. (iv) Conduct an economic and feasibility analysis to evaluate the financial and practical viability of the process. Finally, (v) iterate and validate the model by refining inputs and verifying results to ensure accuracy and reliability. Figure 1 illustrates the smart sequence and highlights the key stages involved in each step.

Figure 1. Smart steps sequence for rapid learning in SuperPro designer.

2.3 Description of the course assessment

In the evaluation of progress for SuperPro Designer strategies aimed at rapid learning, various criteria and evaluation instruments are employed. These include an analysis of projects carried out by students, and a post-course survey. The data collection and analysis procedures utilize both qualitative and quantitative methods, supported using statistical analysis software to ensure accurate and comprehensive assessment.

To evaluate the effectiveness of the active learning strategy implemented with SuperPro Designer, a comparative analysis of student performance was conducted using (i) two quizzes, (ii) one main activity and (iii) a final project. The first quiz was administered during the initial week of the course, when students had received introductory training in the use of the software, while the second was delivered in the second week, after comprehensive instruction and more hours in practical engagement. In both cases, students were tasked with addressing a bioprocess design challenge under defined production and operational constraints using SuperPro Designer. The activity consisted of designing and simulation of the process for protein recovery that was done during a previous experimental course. Finally, the last evaluation was designing and simulating a case of study based on carotenoids, lipids and lipases production. The distribution of grades of the assignments was first assessed using the Anderson-Darling test, which confirmed a deviation from normality (p -value < 0.005 in both cases). Accordingly, the Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test was employed to evaluate the differences between paired samples (Coakley & Conover, 2000). A statistically significant improvement in performance was observed (p -value < 0.005), suggesting that proficiency in bioprocess design was enhanced through structured use of the software over the course period.

The post-course survey was designed to evaluate students' perceptions of the most critical factors for strategic bioprocess design and planning using SuperPro Designer. The survey consisted of seven questions, structured to prompt reflection on key aspects, constraints, and design criteria encountered during process modeling depicted in Table 1.

Table 1. Post-course survey regarding SuperPro designer use during the course.

Question	Response Type
How did you use SuperPro Designer to dimension the bioreactor in your project? Reflect on the process you followed and indicate the key parameters you configured in the software.	Multiple choice, closed
What large-scale analysis did you perform with SuperPro Designer, and how did you ensure the process would be efficient at a large-scale?	Multiple choice, closed
How did SuperPro Designer help you identify and optimize the bioreactor's operating conditions? At the end of the list of possible answers, provide a specific example of an optimization performed in the "other" option.	Multiple choice, closed
How did you evaluate the economic feasibility of the bioprocess using SuperPro Designer? What economic factors did you consider?	Multiple choice, closed
What environmental impact of the bioprocess did you analyze with SuperPro Designer? Write in the "other" box how this influenced the design and operation decisions of the bioreactor.	Multiple choice, closed
How did you integrate product and market niche aspects into your analysis with SuperPro Designer?	Open text
What industrial property considerations (such as patents) did you take into account when planning the biotechnological project with SuperPro Designer? How did these considerations influence process development?	Multiple choice, closed

Students could select all applicable responses, and some questions included an "Other" option for free-text input. Each question and its corresponding answers were grouped into three overarching topics: *Bioreactor*

Design, Bioprocess Scale-Up, and Industrial & Regulatory Considerations. To enable a structured analysis, individual responses were further classified into conceptual subcategories within each topic. These subcategories are presented in Table 2. A detailed classification of the answers and questions is available upon request to the corresponding author.

Table 2. Post-course survey topic and conceptual subcategory division.

Bioprocess Scale-Up	Bioreactor Design	Industrial and Regulatory Considerations
Process Optimization	Bioreactor Configuration and Modes	Economic and Operational Costs
Bioprocess Fundamentals	Operational Parameters	Environmental and Sustainability Considerations
Scale-Up Strategies	Resource Management	Intellectual Property (IP) Strategy
Reactor Mode Considerations	Process Performance & Risk	No IP or Regulatory Considerations
Other	Mass & Energy Transfer Considerations	Waste management and Disposal Costs
		Regulatory and Compliance Considerations

Of the 40 students enrolled across both groups, 32 completed the survey. The survey was administered via Google Forms, and all answers were returned in textual format. For ease of quantification, a binary matrix was generated using Python to represent selections. Frequency-based metrics were used to evaluate the relative emphasis placed on each conceptual category, computed as the proportion of selections for each subcategory relative to the total number of responses within a given topic. Proficiency-based segmentation was not applied at this stage of the analysis. All code and processed datasets used for the analysis are available in the supplementary materials.

3 Results and Discussion

During the first two weeks, students underwent a full immersion in learning the characteristics of SuperPro Designer. The course began with an overview of the main menus and tools, delivered through direct instruction by the professor. The structure of the classes combined theory with practical exercises to explain the functionality of the software systematically. Additionally, students were provided with digital resources to enhance their learning experience. These resources included access to tutorials, instructional videos, and online forums (available in the supplementary material provided in the statements section). At the end of the first and second week, students were asked to complete two quizzes regarding the comprehension of the software, in the first quiz a simulation of a bioreactor for growth of *E. coli* was asked and in the second quiz a process for separation of the biomass produced in the bioreactor through centrifugation and microfiltration was asked. It was observed that from quiz 1 to quiz 2, the proportion of students reaching the proficient level increased from 44.4% to 69.4% of the population. The solid level also increased from 11.1% to 13.8%, while the basic and incipient levels diminished from 22.22% to 2.7% and from 25% to 13.8%, respectively. At the end of the first two weeks of the courses, it was observed that most of the students exhibited a competence level in SuperPro Designer in the following aspects: they became familiar with the software menus; they can define a process flow diagram; they know how to enter data for compounds, new compounds, and mixtures; they can define operating conditions in equipment such as bioreactors, centrifuges, microfiltration units, and homogenizers; and they can run simulations and analyse data. These are basic knowledge of the software corresponding to the first three steps of the smart sequence described in Figure 1. At this point, the students were ready to

improve their skills in SuperPro Designer, and they were asked to gather into teams of 3 to 4 members and complete the first activity based on a simulation of a full process for protein recovery as shown in Figure 2. This activity was completed during the third week of the course. Although the activity was discussed and developed in teams, the students were asked to deliver the main results of the simulations individually. Compared to Quiz 2, the results from the activity showed a decrease in the proportion of students reaching the proficient level (33.3%), with the rest of the students grouped into the solid level (47.0%), basic level (16.6%), and, surprisingly, the incipient level decreased to 2.7% of the students. The decrease in the proficient level can be linked to the high level of difficulty of the task. As illustrated in Figure 2, the production and recovery of a chromoprotein was used as a common task for all students and served as an evaluation tool to enhance the learning in SuperPro Designer during the third week of the course. All students performed the analysis, synthesis, and design of the studied bioprocesses, incorporating the basic stages of upstream (inoculum preparation and seed bioreactors), bioreaction (production bioreactor), and downstream (recovery and purification of the target biomolecule). It is also worth noting that this specific process was carried out on a laboratory scale during previous laboratory courses which facilitated the comprehension of the stages of the process.

For the remaining two weeks of the course, the case studies of carotenoids, lipids, and lipases production process were presented and assigned to the students, who were previously gathered in teams. For the case study of lipids, the oleaginous yeast *Schwanniomyces occidentalis* was used as a microorganism for which kinetic and stoichiometric characterization was done at a laboratory scale in a previous course. Among the main results obtained by the students during simulations of large-scale production of lipids, they proposed an inoculum development starting from 1 L bioreactor, followed by scales to 10 L and 100 L, adjusting operational parameters. Also, they use the physicochemical properties of lipids to develop a downstream process based on the extraction process for recovery and purification of lipids. From economic analysis they found that high investment and operational costs limit the process' profitability, although strategies such as selling by-products and optimizing processes are suggested to improve economic viability. Students also highlighted the importance of incorporating innovations in metabolic engineering to maximize triglyceride accumulation. The case study for lipase production aimed to design, characterize, and evaluate the economic aspects of producing a recombinant lipase for the leather tanning industry.

Figure 2. Typical flow process diagram obtained from SuperPro Designer. The diagram corresponds to the process for chromoprotein production and recovery.

Enzymatic tanning using lipases offers an eco-friendly alternative, yielding more uniform and flexible leather. The project proposal by the students in SuperPro Designer aimed to produce 25 tons of lipase annually using a 20 m³ main fermenter and a 2 m³ seed fermenter. Kinetic parameters were retrieved during laboratory-scale experiments by the students, as well as yields of protein recovery and purification during the downstream

process and used to simulate the stages of lipase production in SuperPro Designer, including fermentation, cell rupture, and ultrafiltration, coupled with financial analysis and logistics optimization. The scenario simulated in SuperPro by the students proved most efficient and economically viable, producing 23.7 tons of lipase per year with the highest ROI (43.4%) and the shortest payback period (2.3 years). Finally, a theoretical project was proposed for producing carotenoids using *Rhodotorula glutinis* for trout feed. A process train was designed in SuperPro Designer based on literature data. The annual demand for yeast was calculated, and the process includes fermentation in a stirred-tank bioreactor, centrifugation to separate cells from the medium, and spray drying to maintain carotenoids within the yeast cells. A simplified downstream process was chosen, producing dry yeast enriched with carotenoids as the final product. The industrial-scale bioreactor was designed considering a productivity rate, resulting in a 5622 L bioreactor to generate the necessary yeast amount. According to the results of the evaluation for the projects delivered by the students, it was found that 65.1 % of the students reached a solid level in the usage of SuperPro designer, the remaining were distributed in 17.2 % in proficient level, 13.4 % in basic level and 4.2 % in incipient level.

The results of the post-course survey are summarized in Figure 3, which illustrates the weighted frequency of selections across the three major topics related to bioprocess design: Bioprocess Scale-Up (Figure 3A), Bioreactor Design (Figure 3B), and Industrial & Regulatory Considerations (Figure 3C). Each response was categorized into conceptual subcategories to facilitate a structured interpretation of students' perceived learning outcomes following their use of SuperPro Designer. Regarding Bioprocess Scale-Up, students most frequently selected answers related to process optimization and foundational scale-up strategies. This trend suggests that SuperPro Designer was perceived as an effective tool for conceptualizing scaling challenges and opportunities for production improvement. The platform appeared to support the development of strategic thinking skills, particularly those associated with evaluating constraints and enhancing process efficiency within an industrial context. In the case of Bioreactor Design, students demonstrated high engagement with structural and operational aspects, as reflected by the strong selection of items in the Resource Management and Operational Parameters categories. This indicates that the course enabled students to grasp not only engineering considerations but also the logistical and economic implications associated with bioreactor operation. Nevertheless, *Mass & Energy Transfer Considerations* were among the least frequently selected categories. This disparity may be attributed to the limited capabilities of SuperPro Designer in modeling dynamic transfer phenomena. Since the software mainly relies on static user input rather than mechanistic calculations, an accurate consideration of these parameters requires prior theoretical knowledge and an awareness of the assumptions underlying simulation-based design.

For *Industrial & Regulatory Considerations*, the analysis revealed a strong emphasis on economic and sustainability-related factors, with relatively less attention paid to regulatory and intellectual property constraints. This imbalance may reflect students' greater familiarity with economic frameworks, as well as the non-mandatory implementation of regulatory and IP-related fields in SuperPro Designer. While the software allows users to define costs for waste disposal, assign waste streams, or incorporate royalty payments, these features are optional and often underutilized unless explicitly prompted by instructional content. Overall, the survey results suggest that SuperPro Designer effectively reinforced key engineering competencies such as process optimization, economic assessment, and scale-up planning. At the same time, the findings highlight the need to provide additional pedagogical support for underrepresented yet critical topics, including mass transfer, regulatory affairs, and intellectual property management. These areas could be better addressed through complementary teaching methods, such as targeted workshops, guest lectures, or integration with more specialized tools. This reinforces the importance of using SuperPro Designer not as a standalone solution, but as a practical component of a broader curriculum aimed at developing comprehensive bioprocess design expertise.

Figure 3. Post course survey results on the most relevant aspects for bioprocess design using SuperPro Designer divided by topics: Bioprocess Scale-Up (A), Bioreactor Design (B), Industrial & Regulatory Considerations (C).

4 Conclusions and perspectives

This study represents a pioneering effort in systematically integrating SuperPro Designer into undergraduate Biotechnology Engineering education. To enhance the learning experience, a structured sequence of steps was developed to guide rapid software mastery and encourage students to connect simulation with prior laboratory work. This approach enabled students to transform experimental results into robust scale-up proposals, deepening their understanding of bioprocess engineering. By embedding SuperPro Designer within a Project-Based Learning (PjBL) framework, the course fostered a hands-on, collaborative environment that mirrors real-world engineering practice. This combination not only enhanced students' technical proficiency but also developed key transversal competences such as critical thinking, autonomous learning, and strategic decision-making. The findings align with broader trends in engineering education, highlighting how structured PjBL models can promote deeper learning and better prepare students for industry-relevant challenges. Younger engineering programs seeking to strengthen simulation-based pedagogy may benefit from adopting similar integrative strategies to bridge theory, experimentation, and application.

Declarations

The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose. All participating students were informed at every stage of the study, and their identities remained anonymous. The research conducted only involved the collection of data from various courses where these strategies were implemented. All students participated equally in the study, and there was no differentiation in their treatment. Not any of the students' human rights were compromised. The study adhered to the standard protocols of the Tec 21 educational model of Tecnológico de Monterrey, which continuously students with challenging classes (<https://internationalfaculty.tec.mx/sites/g/files/vgjovo1851/files/tec21-model.pdf>). The study has been approved by the Department of Bioengineering at Tecnológico de Monterrey, Campus Estado de México. Publication has been authorized as an education innovation practice in the institution.

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